

Impact Evaluation of eKitabu's Interventions for Deaf Learners

Endline Report | Feb 2024

Acronyms

- DST: Digital Story Time
- KSL: Kenyan Sign Language
- KOL: Kentalis Observation Tool

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A large group of young African children, likely students, are shown in a crowd. They are wearing blue school uniforms and are looking upwards with expressions of interest and anticipation. The background is slightly blurred, emphasizing the children in the foreground.

Executive Summary

Executive Summary

This report presents the results from the final phase of an evaluation study examining eKitabu's initiatives in three Kenyan primary schools. It evaluates the impact of DST videos and the hiring of DST-trained teachers on student reach and learning outcomes.

Key findings:

- DST videos and teachers have promising influence on learning outcomes and reach. This underscores the importance of accessible multimedia in schools, especially for differently-abled learners.
- DST Teachers are central to the success of educational multimedia content. When DST teachers are engaged, learner engagement, social development, and learning outcomes improve. Further, regular teachers highlight the critical role of DST teachers and desire the latter's continued presence in schools.
- Teachers need to be motivated to use the KOL tool. Though most teachers use the tool, their readiness for assessment varies. Understanding teachers' challenges when implementing the assessment tool and addressing them through training is essential.
- Accessible multimedia educational content and well-trained, engaged teachers enhance the learning experience for learners. eKitabu's intervention is a step in the right direction; further research with a larger sample size and increased intervention exposure time is necessary to draw more definitive conclusions and nuanced recommendations.

Background

Includes engagement overview, study design, objectives of report, and timeline.

Background

eKitabu has developed an EdTech innovation to improve the accessibility and quality of educational content for children with and without disabilities. As part of this initiative, they are deploying interventions which encompass:

- **Digital Story Time (DST) Videos-** Educational video content provided in sign language for deaf learners.
- **DST Teachers-** Hiring teachers who are deaf and fluent in sign language.

The innovation aims to improve learning outcomes for deaf or hard-of-hearing learners across Kenya. They are currently piloting the innovation in five schools for deaf learners. eKitabu tracks learning outcomes for learners via an independent assessment tool administered by teachers, as there is no official standardized assessment in Kenya to measure a child's ability to communicate in sign language.

Engagement Overview

In 2023, iGravity engaged Busara to conduct an impact evaluation of eKitabu's project. The impact evaluation involved a **Difference-in-Difference (DiD) quasi-experimental study design**. We collected data on key outcome variables (performance and class sizes) during the baseline (pre-intervention in July) and end-line (post-intervention in January) phases.

We also collected data after the implementation period (at the midline in September) to better understand how teachers interacted with the interventions during the exposure periods.

Study Design: Difference-in-Difference

- Difference in Difference (DiD) designs estimate the effect of an intervention by comparing the changes in outcomes over time between a population that is receiving the intervention (**treatment group**) and one that is not (**control group**).
- We chose DiD for this study because:
 1. Even with a small sample size, we can rigorously detect the difference between the treatment and control groups. This is key for our study since we only have three schools in the treatment group and two in the control group.
 2. Randomization is not possible in this study. DiD does not require randomization to detect program effects.

Assumption: Parallel Trend Assumption

In the absence of the treatment, the difference between the control and treatment group should be constant over time. That is, the two groups would have parallel trends. This means that for our study, the trends of the outcome variables should be parallel between the treatment and control groups over time.

- Control group
- Treatment group
- - Counterfactual group (expected treatment)

Study Design: Difference-in-Difference

Data Collection Sources:

1. **Administration data:** Comprised of school enrollment, serving as indicators for assessing the intervention's **reach**. Teachers and the eKitabu team collected and shared this data.
2. **KOL tool data:** Captures **learning gains** collected by teachers and the eKitabu team for students in both treatment and control groups.
3. **Survey data:** In addition to the above data that inform the outcome measures, we gathered insights directly from teachers through surveys to **uncover how the intervention influenced results**—like if a new teaching method boosted student scores by enhancing engagement or comprehension—and to **understand the school context** shaping these outcomes.

Study limitations

Limited sample size:

This reduces the statistical power of the study, making it challenging to detect significant effects of the intervention.

Short intervention exposure period:

This may not allow sufficient time for the intervention's effects to manifest.

Endline Objective

To **measure the impact** of DST videos and employing DST teachers on the **reach, and learning outcomes** of deaf and hard-of-hearing learners.

To **explore teachers' experiences** interacting with DST videos and teachers and the KOL tool. These insights will enrich the impact evaluation findings, **contextualize** them, and offer **feedback** to refine the interventions and KOL tool.

Study Design: Workstreams

Sample Summary

Total | 29 respondents

Total number of learners at endline

School	Tumutumu	Kaaga	Kerugoya	Kitui	Machakos	Total
Count	44	73	60	30	59	266

Total number of learners assessed using KOL at endline

School	Tumutumu	Kaaga	Kerugoya	Kitui	Machakos
PP1	10	29	16	2	11
PP2	9	19	13	5	11
Grade 1	14	10	15	5	16
Grade 2	11	15	16	18	21
Total	44	73	60	30	59

Impact of the intervention on reach and learning outcomes

Implementing DST videos and employing DST teachers has the potential to increase reach within schools

- We observe a **positive treatment effect** of 1.92 points within the treatment arm, indicating increased reach. However, due to our study’s limited sample size of teachers and schools, statistical significance is not evident¹.
- These findings suggest promising **potential for the DST teachers and videos to increase the enrollment of learners in the schools.**

1. This means that because we looked at a small number of schools, the data we collected wasn't enough to prove that our findings are reliable or significant from a statistical standpoint.

Implementing DST videos and employing DST teachers has the potential to enhance communication skills among learners

- We find a **positive treatment effect** of 0.22 points. This indicates that being in the treatment arm is associated with an improvement in communication skills among learners. However, our results don't show a clear statistical impact due to the relatively low number of schools for this study.
- These findings suggest the **promising potential** for the DST teachers and videos to improve communication skills among learners after controlling for other variables such as gender and grades.

Implementing DST videos and employing DST teachers has the potential to improve understanding of KSL grammar among learners

1. This means that because we looked at a small number of schools, the data we collected wasn't enough to prove that our findings are reliable or significant from a statistical standpoint.

- We find a **positive treatment effect** of 0.02 points. This indicates that being in the treatment arm is associated with an improvement in understanding KSL grammar among learners. However, our results don't show a clear statistical impact, due to the relatively low number of schools for this study (1).
- These findings suggest the **promising potential** for the DST teachers and videos to improve communication skills among learners after controlling for other variables such as gender and grades.

Implementing DST videos and employing DST teachers has the potential to improve the expression of KSL grammar among learners

- We find a **positive treatment effect** of 0.08 points. This indicates that being in the treatment arm is associated with an improvement in expressive KSL grammar among learners. However, our results don't show a clear statistical impact, due to the relatively low number of schools for this study (1).
- These findings suggest the **promising potential** for the DST teachers and videos to improve communication skills among learners after controlling for other variables such as gender and grades.

1. This means that because we looked at a small number of schools, the data we collected wasn't enough to prove that our findings are reliable or significant from a statistical standpoint.

Summary of impact evaluation findings

Finding	Recommendation
<p>DST videos and teachers positively influence learning outcomes in the three sections-communication skills, understanding, and expression of KSL grammar.</p>	<p>There is potential for eKitabu’s intervention to positively impact learners. We recommend testing the intervention on a larger sample to draw more definitive conclusions and identify more nuanced areas for recommendations.</p>
<p>Similarly, the DST videos and teachers are associated with increased enrollment for the treated classes.</p>	<p>DST videos and teachers have the potential to influence reach positively. We recommend conducting the intervention with a larger sample size and extending the exposure duration to ensure sufficient time for observing changes.</p>

Engagement with interventions

DST videos and teachers

Majority of teachers utilize DST videos for teaching, with regular incorporation observed among nearly half of them

Have used DST videos

Has not used DST videos

Frequency of using DST videos

- Of the 21 teachers in the treatment group, 15 (71%) have been using the DST videos for teaching.
- The majority of these teachers (11/15) began using the DST videos in July, while the remaining 4 started in September. Given that there was a holiday break in August, this does not pose much of an effect on the video utilization rate.
- Among those who utilize DST videos:
 - ❖ All 15 teachers use DST videos at least once a week.
 - ❖ 8 of the 15 teachers use DST videos more than once a week.

The schools actively coordinate and integrate DST videos into the schedule, employing a multi-disciplinary approach to enhance comprehension and reinforce learning.

- DST videos are primarily scheduled for afternoons, often taking place within computer labs. Schools mostly use laptops to project videos.
- In addition to standalone sessions, DST videos are occasionally integrated into English and KSL classes, suggesting a multi-disciplinary approach to their use.
- Some teachers enhance the DST video sessions with supplementary materials such as flashcards and photos. This indicates a varied instructional approach aimed at reinforcing learning outcomes.
- There is a seamless integration of DST video usage within the existing school schedule. This suggests that the timing and frequency of DST video sessions are well-coordinated with other academic activities.

"[DST videos] it's in a timetable, but in a different lesson. In the timetable, we allocate..."

"...we made a program, my class goes to the computer room on Tuesday afternoon..."

The DST videos boost student engagement, comprehension, and motivation, highlighting the importance of multimedia tools in enhancing learning experiences.

- Integrating DST videos into classes suggests increased learner engagement and interaction compared to traditional lessons without visualization aids. Teachers reported that the learners actively participate by answering questions, discussing images, and narrating stories during DST video sessions, demonstrating improved comprehension and retention of information.
- The DST videos' graphics and visuals usually enhance learners' excitement and motivation, leading to heightened participation and vocabulary acquisition.
- One teacher described classes without DST videos as dull, with learners struggling to concentrate and lacking enthusiasm.

“...They were enjoying and participating...”

“...they all pay attention because they want to see the story in the videos. They want to watch. All of them are paying attention...”

DST Videos' quality and quantity perceptions

Teachers like the videos because they are clear and engaging, and include helpful features like clear audio and facial expressions that aid student understanding and engagement.

- The teachers like the **clarity and depth of information presented** in the videos, noting that they engage learners effectively with appealing visuals, clear audio, and relatable content.
- **Facial expressions and sign language** are particularly praised for enhancing understanding and engagement among learners. The **length of the videos** is deemed appropriate, allowing for student comprehension and interaction.
- Additionally, the videos include **glossary words** at the beginning and **questions** at the end to help reinforce learning and assess comprehension.

“...The way the signers are presenting the content. They are really explaining it nicely until even the learners can understand without even explaining. The signers are very good. And even the videos are very clear...”

“...I like the way they do the facial expressions.”

“...I like about the visuals. Their appearance and the explanation and also can you say they are satisfactory and to the level of the learner...”

Teachers want greater alignment between DST videos and textbooks, along with adjustments in pacing and contextualization to accommodate all learners.

“...The first thing that I don't like is when I come to class, they don't match with the stories or the content in the textbooks...”

“...The story is in English and the explanation is in KSL...”

“...They're not very clear. Those videos, I don't know how we can put it, but how they can be related to what the children is familiar with...”

- Teachers express a need for more **DST stories that align with textbook content**, particularly in mathematics, and a desire for a greater variety of videos covering all subjects.
- Concerns are raised about the **advanced level of materials**, specifically for Grade 1 learners, and the **pacing of the videos**, which is too fast for a few.
- Suggestions include ensuring that the videos' contents are contextualized and produced in exact English to match textbooks. However, DST content aims to improve KSL acquisition.
- Addressing this **mismatch in expectations** involves training teachers on utilizing the videos and how they support learning English.

DST teachers actively boosted student engagement, learning, and social development, leading other teachers to desire their continued presence in the school.

The end-line survey was only administered to **2 DST teachers**.

Impact of DST Teachers on Student Engagement and Learning:

- Both DST teachers integrated well into their schools and connected effectively with learners. As a result, learners demonstrated increased participation, concentration, and confidence, showing notable advancements in reading, signing, and interactive learning activities under the guidance of DST teachers.
- Significant improvements in student engagement, signing proficiency, and overall language acquisition were noted, with the other teachers commending the enjoyable classes and collaborative atmosphere fostered by the DST teachers.

Recognition of Positive Effects and Desire for Continued Presence:

- The other teachers acknowledged DST teachers' positive effects on learners' academic and social development. Several teachers expressed a desire for the continued presence of DST teachers in the school due to their significant impact on learners' learning and the overall school environment.

“...Learners are very happy about the teacher, their signing has improved...”

“...Learners understand the teacher easily because she is an expert in signing...”

“...Very good at interacting with learners and the staff...”

KOL Tool Feedback

Most of the surveyed teachers have received training in using the KOL tool. High utilization rates across different grades, particularly in PP2, indicate widespread application of assessments.

- Of the 24 teachers surveyed, 22 (91.67%) reported receiving training on utilizing the KOL tool. The two teachers who had yet to receive training on KOL were all from Kerugoya school.
- Among the 22 trained individuals, 20 have applied the KOL tool for assessments, predominantly for actual assessments rather than practice sessions. The two teachers who have yet to use KOL for assessment were from Kaaga School.
- Of those who utilized the KOL tool, 70% (14 out of 20) have employed it more than once.
- PP2 exhibits the highest engagement, with seven teachers actively utilizing the KOL tool for assessments, while PP1, Grade 1, and Grade 2 each have six teachers actively involved.

Teachers' assessment readiness varies due to time constraints, process complexity, and incomplete learner background information, despite some finding the KOL tool easy to use.

Experience using the KOL tool to assess deaf or hard-of-hearing learners			
Very Easy	Easy	Neutral	Challenging
3	8	6	3

“...I find it hard to administer the tool to learners with intellectual disability as most of the time their skill is either approaching or below. Sometimes it's not the learner's fault, but I would want a better way to administer to them....”

“...It is time-consuming when you have a large class...”

- Teachers display varying levels of readiness for conducting assessments.
- While some exhibit confidence and readiness, citing adequate training and experience as contributing factors, others acknowledge the need for additional time, practice, training, and relevant materials to improve their preparedness and confidence in assessing the learners.

What makes administering the assessment challenging for some teachers?

- Administering assessments presents challenges primarily due to **time constraints and the complexity of the process**. The teachers note that it becomes particularly time-consuming, especially with **large classes** or **learners with other disabilities**.
- Additionally, the length of the assessment tools increases the challenge of time management during the assessment process. This is hindered further by challenges from **incomplete learner background information** provided by parents, complicating teachers' ability to conduct assessments effectively.

Learnings For Phase 2

Consideration for Phase 2:

Consider **extending the exposure period** of interventions to enhance their effectiveness on learning outcomes and reach.

Conduct **workshops and training sessions** with teachers to:

1. Improve **teacher motivation and buy-in** by highlighting the value of learning Kenyan Sign Language (KSL) and illustrating how to enrich textbook content presented in exact English with DST videos in KSL. Teacher motivation is a key indicator of student outcomes². Understanding and defining what motivates teachers is crucial to designing interventions that boost their motivation and engagement.
2. Simplifying the administration process will improve their **readiness to administer the KOL tool** and simultaneously change the perception that using it is difficult and complex.

Incorporate **qualitative research** to contextualize the impact evaluation findings. This can shed light on the intervention utilization and KOL tool administration experience.

Schools should devise strategies to ensure they **gather complete and detailed information about learners** from their parents and guardians in order to allow teachers to assess the learners adequately.

2. Bardach, L., & Klassen, R. M. (2021). Teacher motivation and student outcomes: Searching for the signal. *Educational Psychologist*, 56(4), 283-297.

Recommendations:

To improve the **DST Videos**, the teachers suggest:

- Simplifying the content by reducing the vocabulary to avoid overwhelming learners.
- Broadening and aligning the content more closely to the classroom textbooks. Include **mathematics, alphabets, shapes, and animals in the video content.**
- Increasing the **number** of available videos to cover more content.

To improve the **KOL tool**, the teachers suggest:

- Incorporating measures to assess color use and drawing abilities to **accommodate children with other or multiple disabilities.**
- Simplifying language and reducing the number of questions to improve efficiency while administering the tool.
- Aligning assessment timing with learners' **schedules.**

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